

The Impacts of the Travel Service Quality: A Study in the Mongolian Tourism Sector

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ABSTRACT

This study of the purpose is to assess tourist perceptions of quality tourism services provided in the Mongolian tourism sector. In this study, 3 hypotheses were processing are suggested a study model. The research question was obtained from tourists via a survey that yielded 130 usable questionnaires, these data were analyzed using regression to determine the relationship between service quality. As a result, this study showed service quality plays an important role in tourism by increasing the level of tourist services. The results in this study support the evidence that there are positive impacts of components of tourism products on tourist service quality.

KEYWORDS: Service quality, tourism, Mongolia

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I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of the world's top and fastest-growing markets, playing a very important role in the economy and supporting another economy's growth (Osman and Sentosa, 2013). In 2012, the tourism and travel sector outperformed the global economy, growing faster than manufacturing, retail, financial services, and communications. The sector has raised its total contribution to GDP by 3% and increased the number of workers by 5 million to 260 million.

Tourism sector plays a significant role in the national economy in Mongolia and contributes significantly to the country's GDP relative to other industries. Mongolia is the last nomadic culture in the world. In additionally, about 40% of its people era nomadic or semi-nomadic.

Mongolian nomadic cultures, history and wonderful natural resources are the powerful resources to advertise local and foreign tourists and develop tourism, so the number of travelers to Mongolia is growing. It got 552812 visitors in 2017. In this case, it was about 16 percent higher than last year's tourists. In addition, the calculation of tourism profit is increased by 17.5%. In European, 37% of tourists visit to see beautiful places, 27% visit to introduce nomadic culture, and 20% visit to introduce Mongolian great history.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Service quality has been defined in some earlier studies to the extent that the service fulfills customer needs or expectations (Lewis and Mitchell, 1990; Dotchin and

Oakland, 1994). Thus Zeithaml et al. (1996) conceptualized the quality of service as the overall impression of the customer of service weakness or supremacy. Therefore, service quality was often described as the discrepancy between perceived service performance anticipated and actual service performance (Bloemer et al., 1999; Kara et al., 2005).

Parasuraman et al. (1988) developed the SERVQUAL model to assess the quality of service in five dimensions, including 22 items: reliability, tangible, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. These dimensions have specific service features that are linked to customer expectations. In the marketing context, the SERVQUAL scale was developed and supported by the Marketing Science Institute (Parasuraman et al. 1986).

Although, this design was used as an instrument in various industry studies, the SERVQUAL received a lot of criticism from other academics (e.g., Cronin and Taylor, 1992; Brown et al., 1993). However, due to the differences in industry characteristics, there are many researchers opposed using SERVQUAL to measure service quality. Other previous research confirmed the applicability of the SERVQUAL tool in the tourism sector (Fick and Ritchie, 1991; Yuan et al., 2005; Shaikh and Khan, 2011).

Medlik and Middleton (1973) reported that the tourism product is to be considered as an amalgam of three main

components of attractions, facilities at the destination and accessibility of the destination. For example, the tourist item is 'not as an airline seat or hotel bed, or relaxing on a sunny beach... but as an amalgam of many components, or While Middleton and Clarke (2001) suggested that the overall brand consists of five main components: destination facilities and services, accessibility of the destination, destination attractions and environment, images of the destination, and Price to the customer.

➤ **Destination facilities and services**

These are the component elements in the destination that allow visitors to stay and enjoy the destination. They include: accomodation unit: holiday villages, apartments, villas, campsites, caravan parks, hostels, , farms, guesthouses condominiums. Restaurants, bars, and cafes: ranging from fast food through to luxurious restaurants. Transport at the destination : coaches, cycle hire, car rental, taxi. Sports/interest activities: ski schools, sailing schools, golf clubs, and spectator stadiums; arts and crafts centers and studies of nature. Other facilities: schools of culture, clubs of fitness. Retail outlets:, travel agents, souvenirs, shops camping supplies. Other services include information services, equipment rental, tourism police.

➤ **Accessibility of the destination**

These are the component elements including the product's private and public transport aspects that determine the speed, cost and convenience with which a traveler can leave his place of residence and arrive at a destination chosen. They include Infrastructure: roads, car parking, airports, railways, seaport, marinas, inland waterways. Equipment: size, the scope of vehicles for public transport. Operational factors: regulated routes, service speed, charged rates, and paid road tolls. Government regulations: the range of transportation regulatory controls (Middleton and Hawkins, 1998).

A study conducted by Karim and Geng-Qing Chi (2010) confirmed that the food image of destinations positively influenced the intention of travelers to visit.

While Awaritefe(2004) found that in a third world country the most prominent motivations for choosing tourist destinations are: self-actualization in an appreciative, educational or cultural context and leisure / recreational

pursuits. The attractiveness of the destination, quality services, facilities/amenities, favorable location, and accessibility of centers also emerged as essential considerations in tourist destination choice.

➤ **Destination attractions and environment**

These are the section elements within the destination that largely determine the choice of tourists to visit that destination and influence their motivations. These include: natural attractions: scenery, seascape, beaches, climate, flora and fauna, and other destination geographical features and natural resources. Built attractions: buildings and tourism infrastructure, including historical and modern architecture; monuments; promenades, parks and gardens, convention centers, marinas, ski slopes, industrial archaeology, generally managed tourist attractions, golf courses, specialty shops, and thematic retail area. Cultural attractions: religion and art, theatre, history and folklore music, dance, entertainment, museums, etc. Social attractions: resident or host population's way of life and customs, language and social encounters opportunities.

Therefore, the purpose of the study is to assess tourist perceptions of quality tourism services provided in the Mongolian tourism secto. As shown in Figure 1, three main destination dimensions were chosen as factors that could affect the quality of tourist service.

"Fig. 1," Research hypothesis

III. Research hypothesis:

- H1: The facilities (restaurant, souvenir, tour guide) and tourists have a positive relationship.
- H2: Accessibility to destinations (toilet, maps, parking) and tourists have a positive relationship.
- H3: The destination attractions (nomadic culture) and tourists have a positive relationship.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In this study, the questionnaire consisted of one part, and they are including: destination attractions; destination facilities; and accessibility of the destination. The questionnaire was developed using a 5-point Likert-type scale based on the validated scales used in the existing literature, consisting of 20 items as follows. A total number of 130 questionnaires were shared with tourists at Mongolia, the data were collected at the tourist center in Mongolia from October 2018 until November 2019.

V. RESULT

As shown in Table 1, the total number of tourists participating in this study was 130. According to analysis shows, most tourists (63.8%) male and female(36.2%). The majority of tourists age between 25-30 years. Monthly income for the majority of the tourist between was \$552-1288\$. European tourists (43.1%) were the most people visiting Mongolia, followed by Korea tourists (19.2%), USA(16.2%), while Japan and China people (10%) were the less.

Table1. Descriptive statistic

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent %
Gender	Female	47	36.2
	Male	83	63.8
	Total	130	100.0
Age	25	33	25.4
	28	36	27.7
	30	61	46.9
	Total	130	100.0
Montly income	1500000	42	32.3
	2500000	20	15.4
	3000000	34	26.2
	3500000	34	26.2
	Total	130	100.0
Nationality	China	15	11.5
	European	56	43.1
	Japan	13	10.0
	Korea	25	19.2
	USA	21	16.2
	Total	130	100.0

VI. Reliability analysis

This analysis was used to check the variables. Three main factors with 20 items were included in the system. The service quality model was factorially analyzed and items of 24 questions. According to the results shows, Cronbach's value was .969.

Table.2. Reliability analysis

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.969	20

VII. Linear regression analysis

The current analysis tested the main hypothesis by using linear regression analysis. There were very high relationship correlations between all variables of this analysis of the about significant level was (P<.05). Therefore, a linear regression model was necessary to conduct in order to indicate the impact of service quality.(Table.3)

Table.3.Linear regression analysis for the facilities

Linear regression analysis							
Model	R	R ²	Std.error	Beta	t	Sig.	Hypothesis
1	.796	.634	.034	.796	23.011	.000	Support
A. A.Independent variable: the facilities							
B. Dependent variable: service quality							

As shown in Table 3, the results of regression showed that facilities at the destination(restaurant,tour guide, souvinier) had a positive relationship with the quality of service ($\beta = .796$). Previous analysis shows, destination facilities explain (R²) 63.4 % of the variance in service quality, this means destination facilities are a moderate predictor in service quality. As a result, the overall statistical results confirmed that relationship, and therefore hypothesis H1 is supported.

Table.4 Linear regression analysis for accessibility to destinations

Linear regression analysis							
Model	R	R ²	Std.error	Beta	t	Sig.	Hypothesis
1	.687	.473	.066	.687	10.688	.000	Support
A. Independent variable: accessibility							
B. Dependent variable: service quality							

As shown in Table 4, the results of regression showed that accessibility to the destinations(toilet, maps, parking,) had a positive relationship with quality of service ($\beta = .687$). Previous analysis shows, destination facilities explain (R²) 47.3 % of the variance in service quality, this means destination facilities are less predictor in service quality. As a result, the overall statistical results confirmed that relationship, and therefore hypothesis H2 is supported.

Table.5.Linear regression analysis for the destination attractions

Linear regression analysis							
Model	R	R ²	Std.error	Beta	t	Sig.	Hypothesis
1	.687	.473	.066	.687	10.688	.000	Support
A. Independent variable: accessibility							
B. Dependent variable: service quality							

As shown in Table 5, the results of regression showed that attractions at the destination (nomadic culture) had a positive relationship with the quality of service ($\beta = .614$). Previous analysis shows, destination facilities explain (R^2) 37.7 % of the variance in service quality, this means destination facilities are less predictor in service quality. As a result, the overall statistical results confirmed that relationship, and therefore hypothesis H3 is supported.

VIII. Conclusion

According to results shows that service quality (destination facilities, destination accessibility, destination attractions) was a positive effect on the overall tourist. In this study, confirmed that service quality was a positive relationship with tourists. These results suggest that the quality of service can be enhanced by increasing the quality of service across destination facilities, accessibility of destinations, and attractions of destinations. It was also identified that tourists in Mongolia are moderately satisfied with the level of tourism services. In this study, results are considered valuable in assessing the level of their current services to tourism organizations and businesses in Mongolia. Moreover, this study suggests that the quality of tourism services has a positive impact on the quality of service by enhancing the facilitation of destination, the accessibility of destinations and the attractions of destinations.

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